

Assessment of nano-QSPR models of organic contaminant adsorption by carbon nanotubes for ecological impact studies

Alla P. Toropova and Andrey A. Toropov*

IRCCS, Istituto di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri, 20156, Via La Masa 19, Milano, Italy

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Abstract

Adsorption of organic contaminants on carbon nanotubes is very important ecological criterion. Consequently predictive model for this endpoint is useful from point of view of ecological risk assessment. Quantitative Structure–Property Relationships (QSPRs) built up by CORAL software (<http://www.insilico.eu/coral>) are used to develop predictive models for adsorption ($\log K_{oc}$) of organic contaminants by multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs). The statistical characteristics of a CORAL model for external validation set are the following: $n=30$; $r^2=0.8878$; $RMSE=0.475$ (mg/g). The probabilistic scheme of the definition of the domain of applicability for the CORAL models are suggested. The practical aspects of using the CORAL software are discussed.

Key words: Nano-QSPR; Carbon Nanotube; Adsorption; Monte Carlo method; OECD principles

*) Corresponding author

Andrey A. Toropov

Laboratory of Environmental Chemistry and Toxicology, IRCCS - Istituto di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri, Via La Masa 19, 20156 Milano, Italy

Tel: +39 02 3901 4595

Fax: +3902 3901 4735

E-mail: andrey.toropov@marionegri.it

1. Introduction

The estimation of ecological impacts of new industrial pollutants such as organic pollutants [1], pharmaceutical pollutants [2], nanoparticles [3,4], require clear prioritization and characterization of these substances [5,6].

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are nanomaterials exhibiting strong adsorption ability to a wide range of synthetic organic contaminants [7]. However, despite the voluminous research works related to nanomaterials in the literature, the available adsorption data for CNTs still cover only a small part of potential industrial pollutants. Therefore the definition of theoretical approaches to estimate the adsorption ($\log K_{\infty}$, mg/g) of organic contaminants by multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) is an important task of the natural sciences. One of the possible ways to solve this task is the quantitative structure – property relationships (QSPR) based on the descriptors calculated with the molecular graphs [8-10]. Since there are databases available on the Internet [11] where the molecular structure is represented by the simplified molecular input-line entry systems (SMILES) [12-15], the software for QSPR analysis based on the representation of the molecular structure by SMILES [16-25] becomes an attractive alternative of the software based on the molecular graphs.

The present study is aimed to develop and estimate predictive potential of the QSPR models for the adsorption of organic contaminants by MWCNTs which are calculated with using the CORAL software [26], based on the Monte Carlo technique.

2. Method

2.1. Data

The numerical data on the adsorption ($\log K_{\infty}$, mg/g) of organic contaminants (n=59) by MWCNTs taken in the literature [7]. These data were randomly distributed four times into the sub-training, calibration, test, and validation sets. Using these distributions together with the distribution taken in the literature [7] five various QSPR models for the $\log K_{\infty}$ were built up.

2.2. The Monte Carlo technique to build up QSPR model for $\log K_{\infty}$

The optimal descriptors based on the simplified molecular input-line entry system (SMILES) are calculated as the following:

$$DCW(T,N) = \sum CW(SA_k) + CW(NOSP) + CW(BOND) \quad (1)$$

where SA_k are various molecular features extracted from SMILES. The majority of the SA_k are represented by a single symbol, e.g. C, N, O are representations of carbon, nitrogen, and oxygen, respectively. There are however exceptions, e.g. Cl, Br, Ca, which are representations of chlorine, bromine, and calcium, respectively. The NOSP is a molecular descriptor which is a mathematical function of the presence (absence) the following atoms: (i) nitrogen; (ii) oxygen; (iii) sulphur; and

(iv) phosphorus [27]. The BOND is a molecular descriptor which is a mathematical function of the presence (absence) of double, triple, and stereochemical bonds [27]. *Supplementary materials* section (Table S1) contains examples of SA_k , NOSP, and BOND. The $CW(SA_k)$, $CW(NOSP)$, and $CW(BOND)$ are the correlation weight of SA_k , NOSP, and BOND, respectively. The numerical data on the $CW(SA_k)$, $CW(NOSP)$ and $CW(BOND)$ are calculated with the Monte Carlo optimization. In fact, the $CW(SA_k)$, $CW(NOSP)$, and $CW(BOND)$ are some coefficients which are using for calculation with Eq. 1 (*Supplementary materials* section, Table S2). The T is threshold to define two classes of the molecular features represented by the SA_k , NOSP, and BOND: (i) rare; and (ii) active i.e. not rare. The rare SA_k , NOSP, and BOND are not involving in building up model. The N is the number of epochs of the Monte Carlo optimization. The optimization gives numerical data on the $CW(SA_k)$, $CW(NOSP)$, and $CW(BOND)$ which provide maximum for the target function

$$TF = R + R' - ABS(R - R') * 0.01 \quad (2)$$

where R and R' are correlation coefficients between $\log K_{\infty}$ and $DCW(T,N)$ for the training set and calibration set, respectively.

Having the numerical data on the correlation weights, one can carry out the following actions [28-31]:

- (i) the calculating the $DCW(N,T)$ for all substances;
- (ii) calculation by the Least Squares method (using solely the sub-training set) the model for adsorption

$$\log K_{\infty} = C_0 + C_1 \cdot DCW(N,T) \quad (3)$$

- (iii) estimation of the model for the external “invisible” validation set.

Thus, the sub-training set, calibration set, test set, and validation set have special roles [31]: (i) the sub-training set is the “developer” of the model: the using of substances from this set gives the correlation weights; (ii) the calibration set is the “critic” of the model since the numerical data on the $DCW(T,N)$ for substances from this set give possibility to estimate “whether this model can has the predictive potential?”; (iii) substances from the test set are a preliminary “estimator” of the model; and (iv) substances from the validation set are the final estimator of the model since no information on the validation set is involved in building up model.

In order to avoid the overtraining, the CORAL approach of building up of QSPR model should be carried out by means of two phases. The first phase is the definition of the preferable $T^{\#}$ and $N^{\#}$ which give the best statistical quality of the model on the test set (Figure 1). The range of T is (1-3). The range of N is (0-20). The second phase is calculation of the model with using the $T^{\#}$ and $N^{\#}$ and further checking up the model with external validation set.

In fact, the sub-training set, calibration set, and test set are “visible” because data on the substances from these sets are involved in building up model, whereas, the validation set is “invisible” since no information about the substances is involved in building up model.

It is known that the distribution into the “visible” training set (in the described approach it is the structured set which involves three sub-sets with the above-mentioned roles) and “invisible” validation set has apparent influence upon the predictive potential of built up model. In order to compare different splits into the “visible” and “invisible” sub-sets, special criteria were suggested and checked up in this work.

The criterion of statistical significance for SA_k. The measure of statistical quality of molecular features (i.e. SA_k, NOSP, or BOND: for compact description NOSP and BOND are meaning further the "particular case" of SA_k) which are extracted from SMILES is calculated as the following:

$$SA_k - Defect = \begin{cases} \frac{|P_{TRN}(A_k) - P_{TST}(A_k)|}{N_{TRN}(A_k) + N_{TST}(A_k)}, & \text{if } -N_{TST}(A_k) > 0 \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where the $P_{TRN}(SA_k)$ is the probability of presence of the SA_k in SMILES of the sub-training set, i.e.

$$P_{TRN}(SA_k) = N_{TRN}(SA_k) / N_{TRN}$$

The $P_{TRN}(SA_k)$ is the probability of presence of the SA_k in SMILES of the test set, i.e.

$$P_{TST}(SA_k) = N_{TST}(SA_k) / N_{TST}$$

The $N_{TRN}(SA_k)$ is the number (frequency) of SMILES which contain SA_k in the sub-training set;

The N_{TRN} is the total number of SMILES in the sub-training set;

The $N_{TST}(SA_k)$ is the number (frequency) of SMILES which contain SA_k in the test set;

The N_{TST} is the total number of SMILES in the test set.

The logic: if the probability of a molecular feature extracted from SMILES (i.e. the SA_k, NOSP, or BOND) in the sub-training set is equal to the probability of the molecular feature in the test set it is the ideal situation and the defect is zero. However, this situation is not typical, i.e. the difference between the probability of a molecular feature in the sub-training set and the probability of the molecular feature in the test set is not zero. Under such circumstances, the frequency of a

molecular feature in the sub-training set and in the test set also should be taken into account: if these are small then the defect of the molecular feature must be larger. Finally, if SA_k (or NOSP, or BOND) is absent in the test set, the SA_k-defect is maximal. Thus, the measure calculated with Eq. 4 can be used for estimation of the statistical significance of SA_k (as well as NOSP and BOND) involved in building up model.

The criterion definition of domain of applicability for a SMILES. Having the numerical data on the SA_k-defect one can estimate reliability of the model for a SMILES: the basic hypothesis is “the probability of SMILES to be in the domain of applicability is inversely proportional of sum of SA_k-defects

$$\text{Defect} = \sum \text{SA}_k\text{-defect}(\text{SA}_k) + \text{SA}_k\text{-defect}(\text{NOSP}) + \text{SA}_k\text{-defect}(\text{BOND}) \quad (5)$$

If the DefectSMILES calculated with Eq. 5 is equal to zero this is an ideal situation. However in praxis, the ideal situation is rare. Consequently, one should define some limitation for the DefectSMILES value. The possible selection for the limit is the following:

$$\text{DefectSMILES} < 2 * \overline{\text{DefectSMILES}} \quad (6)$$

where $\overline{\text{DefectSMILES}}$ is average of the DefectSMILES for the “visible” set (sub-training, calibration, and test sets).

The inequality 6 should be classified as a semi-qualitative criterion, because the large value of the DefectSMILES is not the guarantee, the prediction for substance represented by the SMILES will be poor, and vice versa, the small value of the DefectSMILES is not the guarantee that the prediction will be good. However, "probabilistic" meaning of this criterion is quite transparent.

3. Results and Discussion

Apul et al. [7] have analyzed split into the training set (n=29) and validation set (n=30, but isophorone has been removed as outlier). The statistical characteristics of models for logK_∞ are represented in Table 1. This split into “visible” training set and “invisible” validation set is poorly appropriated for the CORAL model since majority of compounds are not falls into the domain of applicability according to inequality 6 (Table S3 in *Supplementary materials* section).

Moreover, the split where external validation set and training set contain the same number of compounds most probably is unrealistic one. The realistic split for complex endpoint is distribution of 70-80% into the training set and 20-30% into the external validation set. The distributions examined in this work are Split1, Split2, and Split3. Approximately 80% of compounds are placed in the “visible” part and 20% of compounds are placed in the “invisible” validation part. One can see, the statistical characteristics of these models are quite good. These splits are not identical (Table 2).

In order to compare the predictive potential of the CORAL model with model described by Apul et al. [7] the additional Split4 (analog of split examined in [7]) into the sub-training, calibration, test, and validation sets has been checked up.

The validation set in the Split0 (taken from work [7]) contains 30 compounds, but only fifteen of them fall into the domain of applicability according to the inequality 6. The model calculated for the Split0 is the following:

$$\log K_{\infty} = -2.9333 (\pm 0.0942) + 0.1856 (\pm 0.0035) * DCW(2,4) \quad (7)$$

The validation set in the Split4 contains 30 compounds, all these compounds fall into the domain of applicability according to the inequality 6 (Table 3). The model calculated for the Split4 is the following:

$$\log K_{\infty} = -2.5930 (\pm 0.1962) + 0.2501 (\pm 0.0154) * DCW(2,11) \quad (8)$$

Supplementary Table S3 contains the numerical data on the experimental and calculated with Eq. 7 $\log K_{\infty}$ (Split0). Table 3 contains the numerical data on the experimental and calculated with Eq. 8 $\log K_{\infty}$ (Split4). Figure 2 represents models calculated with Eq.7 and Eq. 8, graphically.

The technical details for described QSPR models are available in *Supplementary materials* section (Table S1- Table S9).

Principles. The CORAL approach is based on the following principles: (i) Building up of QSPR model for an arbitrary split into the training and validation sets can be examined as a random event [31]; (ii) The statistical quality of each QSPR model is a mathematical function of split into the sub-training, calibration, test, and validation sets; (iii) The average statistical quality of QSPR models that is obtained for several splits into training and test sets is a more robust criterion for the estimation of an approach than statistical quality for solely one split, but these splits should be considerably different ones (not identical); (iv) The average statistical quality of a model for external “invisible” validation sets is more significant data than the average statistical quality for “visible” (i.e. substances involved in building up model) sub-training and calibration sets; (v) As rule, the actual predictive potential of a model increases together with the increasing of the number (percentage) of compounds which are placed in the “visible” training set.

According to the above-mentioned principles, the split4 should be interpreted as a “successful split”, in other words, a “successful random event”, from point of view of user of the CORAL software. However, Split1, Split2, and Split3 being different ones (Table 4), have demonstrated that the approach has the predictive potential (Table 1).

Mechanistic interpretation. Having data on several runs of the Monte Carlo optimization (Table 4) one can extract four categories of molecular features (SA_k , NOSP, BOND): (i) features which have only positive values of the correlation weights, these can be classified as promoters of $\log K_{\infty}$

increase; (ii) features which have only negative values of the correlation weights, these can be classified as promoters of $\log K_{\infty}$ decrease; (iii) features which have both positive and negative correlation weights for different runs of the Monte Carlo optimization, these can be classified as features with unclear role; finally, (iv) features which are blocked according to the used threshold. One can see (Table 3) that the presence of aromaticity (indicated by 'c'), absence of double and triple bonds (BOND0000), presence of nitrogen ('N'), and presence of the branching (indicated by brackets) should be classified as stable promoters of the $\log K_{\infty}$ increase, whereas the presence of single cycle ('1'), and the presence of oxygen (NOSP0100) should be classified as stable promoters of $\log K_{\infty}$ decrease. However, the frequencies of molecular features in the sub-training and test sets should be also taken into account. Therefore, the CORAL model has a mechanistic interpretation. Thus, the described models are calculated in accordance with OECD principles [32] (Table 5).

Suggestions. The CORAL software can be used for quantitative structure – property / activity relationships (QSPR/QSAR) analyses of arbitrary endpoints, but (i) SMILES which represent molecular structures must be similar in order to provide the significant part of common features; and they must be different in order to guarantee absence of two or more identical values for the DCW(T,N) calculated with Eq. 1; (ii) one should avoid the consideration of a model based on DCW(0,N), since correlation weights of features which take place solely in the test set are nonsense; (iii) the majority (more than 70%) of available data should be inserted into the “visible” sub-training, calibration, and test sets; (iv) one should examine a group of random and different splits in order to estimate the true predictive potential of a QSPR/QSAR model; and (v) one should prefer simplest model reliable for external validation set: the using of a model that is excellent for “visible” sub-training, calibration, and test sets is not good idea.

Advantages and disadvantages. The possibility to estimate influence of different molecular features extracted from SMILES upon the adsorption of organic contaminants by MWCNTs is an advantage of the approach. It is to be noted that the CORAL software gives possibility of comparison of different methods (i.e. models which are based on different features of molecular structure which are extracted from SMILES and/or from molecular graph). This possibility also should be classified as an advantage of the CORAL models. Finally, using of so-called quasi-SMILES can provide the new paradigm of the QSPR/QSAR analyses related to complex nanomaterials where an endpoint is qualified as mathematical function of different physicochemical as well as biochemical conditions which are able to influence upon this endpoint [33-39]. Disadvantage of the approach is the necessity of considerable time of the calculations especially in the case of large data sets.

It is to be noted, that building up of the large enough databases on nanomaterials is far from completing. However, the number of attempts to develop the databases and software gradually increase. Table 6 contains some links which reflect these attempts.

4. Conclusions

The ability of the CORAL software be a tool for QSPR analysis of numerical data on the adsorption ($\log K_{oc}$, mg/g) of organic contaminants by multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNT) is demonstrated. The CORAL models are calculated in accordance with OECD principles (Table 5).

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Table 1

The statistical characteristics of model for adsorption ($\log K_{oc}$, mg/g) of organic contaminants by multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs).

	Split0 in Ref. [7]	Split0 in this work	Split1	Split2	Split3	Split 4	Average ± Dispersion
Sub-Training set							
n	29	16	15	15	17	15	
r^2	0.88	0.8884	0.8080	0.8114	0.8367	0.6573	0.778±0.071
q^2		0.8636	0.7688	0.7366	0.7861	0.5385	0.707±0.099
RMSE		0.408	0.512	0.497	0.363	0.564	0.484±0.071
F		111	55	56	77	25	
Calibration set							
n		5	23	21	17	7	
r^2		0.8915	0.7598	0.6820	0.8371	0.9037	0.796±0.083
RMSE		0.330	0.530	0.473	0.407	0.317	0.432±0.079
Test set							
n		8	10	12	12	7	
r^2		0.8665	0.8534	0.9141	0.8404	0.8889	0.874±0.029
RMSE		0.551	0.237	0.237	0.255	0.457	0.296±0.093
$\overline{r_m^2}^*$		0.717	0.616	0.883	0.759	0.784	0.760±0.095
$\Delta r_m^2^*$		0.090	0.161	0.018	0.100	0.092	0.093±0.051
Validation set							
n	29**	30	10	11	13	30	
r^2		0.6706	0.9453	0.8844	0.9522	0.8878	0.917±0.031
RMSE	0.48	0.544	0.320	0.379	0.276	0.475	0.362±0.075
All compounds							
n	58**	59	59	59	59	59	
R^2	0.83	0.7544	0.8198	0.8155	0.8573	0.8158	0.827±0.017
RMSE		0.493	0.448	0.415	0.369	0.471	0.426±0.038
T [#]		1	1	1	1	2	
N [#]		14	14	10	11	11	

*) According to Roy et al. [33], $\overline{r_m^2}$ should be larger than 0.5 and Δr_m^2 should be less than 0.2

***) Isophorone (CAS 78-59-1) was excluded from QSPR analysis in work [7].

Table 2

Percentages of identity for random splits.

	Set	Split 1	Split 2	Split 3
Split 1	Training	100.0*	46.7	31.3
	Calibration	100.0	45.5	30.0
	Test	100.0	9.1	18.2
	Validation	100.0	27.3	41.7
Split 2	Training		100.0	43.8
	Calibration		100.0	31.6
	Test		100.0	41.7
	Validation		100.0	8.3
Split 3	Sub-training			100.0
	Calibration			100.0
	Test			100.0
	Validation			100.0

$$* Identity(\%) = \frac{N_{i,j}}{0.5 * (N_i + N_j)} \cdot 100$$

where

$N_{i,j}$ is the number of substances distributed into the same set for both the i-th split and the j-th splits (set = sub-training, calibration, test, and validation) ;

N_i is the number of substances distributed into the set for the i-th split;

N_j is the number of substances distributed into the set for the j-th split.

Table 3

The CORAL model calculated with split4 using Eq. 8. The average $\overline{\text{DefectSMILES}} = 0.42869$. Substance falls into domain of applicability, if Defect less than 0.85737. The distribution of data into the sub-training, calibration, test, and validation sets is indicated by symbol (before CAS) '+', '-', '#', and '*', respectively.

CAS	SMILES	DCW(2,11)	logK _∞ Expr	logK _∞ Calc	Defect	DA*
#85-01-8	<chem>c2cc3ccc1ccccc1c3cc2</chem>	23.74932	3.29	3.3465	0.0648	Y
+90-15-3	<chem>Oc2cccc1ccccc12</chem>	17.29846	0.76	1.7332	0.0660	Y
#121-14-2	<chem>Cc1ccc(cc1[N+](=O)[O-])[N+](O)=O</chem>	20.01813	2.38	2.4134	0.8819	N
-87-66-1	<chem>Oc1cccc(O)c1O</chem>	14.05164	1.18	0.9212	0.1348	Y
-88-06-2	<chem>Clc1cc(Cl)cc(Cl)c1O</chem>	16.27871	1.43	1.4782	0.2185	Y
+106-47-8	<chem>Nc1ccc(Cl)cc1</chem>	10.99256	-0.66	0.1561	1.1139	N
+88-74-4	<chem>O=[N+](O)c1ccccc1N</chem>	13.88251	1.60	0.8789	0.4634	Y
-99-09-2	<chem>O=[N+](O)c1cccc(N)c1</chem>	14.38971	0.72	1.0058	0.5235	Y
#106-44-5	<chem>Cc1ccc(O)cc1</chem>	10.95830	0.06	0.1476	0.1108	Y
-554-84-7	<chem>O=[N+](O)c1cccc(O)c1</chem>	15.86042	0.92	1.3736	0.5306	Y
+103-65-1	<chem>CCc1ccccc1</chem>	13.09832	0.76	0.6828	0.0444	Y
+100-51-6	<chem>OCc1ccccc1</chem>	10.45110	-0.90	0.0207	0.0507	Y
+591-50-4	<chem>Ic1ccccc1</chem>	11.30552	0.88	0.2344	0.0330	Y
+623-12-1	<chem>COc1ccc(Cl)cc1</chem>	12.76190	1.07	0.5986	0.1280	Y
-587-03-1	<chem>Cc1cccc(CO)c1</chem>	11.55590	-0.15	0.2970	0.1146	Y
-108-68-9	<chem>Cc1cc(O)cc(C)c1</chem>	12.06310	0.49	0.4239	0.1747	Y
#89-71-4	<chem>COC(=O)c1ccccc1C</chem>	14.91170	1.12	1.1363	0.1978	Y
#108-43-0	<chem>Oc1cc(Cl)ccc1</chem>	12.16430	0.62	0.4492	0.1242	Y
#99-65-0	<chem>O=[N+](O)c1cccc(c1)[N+](O)=O</chem>	19.42053	1.46	2.2639	0.8781	N
+99-99-0	<chem>Cc1ccc(cc1)[N+](=O)[O-]</chem>	14.61255	1.44	1.0615	0.5205	Y
+591-20-8	<chem>Oc1cc(Br)ccc1</chem>	12.65795	0.79	0.5727	1.1070	N
#106-46-7	<chem>Clc1ccc(Cl)cc1</chem>	15.41992	0.51	1.2634	0.1274	Y
+78-59-1	<chem>O=C1C=C(C)CC(C)(C)C1</chem>	11.05813	0.01	0.1725	0.3459	Y
+91-58-7	<chem>Clc1ccc2ccccc2c1</chem>	20.55409	2.73	2.5474	0.0692	Y
-103-33-3	<chem>N(=N/c1ccccc1)c2ccccc2</chem>	20.42082	2.72	2.5141	1.1943	N
+123-07-9	<chem>CCc1ccc(O)cc1</chem>	11.55590	0.62	0.2970	0.1146	Y
+62-53-3	<chem>Nc1ccccc1</chem>	8.68175	-0.77	-0.4218	1.0366	N
+108-86-1	<chem>Brc1ccccc1</chem>	13.60277	0.50	0.8089	1.0330	N
+100-47-0	<chem>N#Cc1ccccc1</chem>	8.47617	0.04	-0.4732	1.0297	N

*129-00-0	c1ccc2ccc3cccc4ccc1c2c34	26.24873	4.01	3.9716	0.0711	Y
*88-75-5	O=[N+](O)c1ccccc1O	15.35322	0.56	1.2467	0.4705	Y
*106-42-3	Cc1ccc(C)cc1	13.00792	0.26	0.6602	0.1007	Y
*93-89-0	O=C(OCC)c1ccccc1	14.91170	1.14	1.1363	0.1978	Y
*91-20-3	c1cccc2ccccc12	18.75049	1.63	2.0964	0.0521	Y
*92-52-4	c1cc(ccc1)c2ccccc2	21.75710	2.05	2.8483	0.1185	Y
*90-43-7	Oc2ccccc2c1ccccc1	19.79788	1.63	2.3583	0.0723	Y
*71-43-2	c1ccccc1	11.30552	-0.45	0.2344	0.0330	Y
*108-90-7	Clc1ccccc1	13.10912	-0.33	0.6855	0.0502	Y
*120-82-1	Clc1cc(Cl)c(Cl)cc1	17.73073	1.17	1.8413	0.2046	Y
*98-95-3	[O-][N+](=O)c1ccccc1	13.50775	0.33	0.7852	0.4566	Y
*108-95-2	Oc1ccccc1	9.85350	-0.54	-0.1287	0.0469	Y
*120-80-9	Oc1ccccc1O	11.69897	0.21	0.3328	0.0609	Y
*99-08-1	Cc1cc(ccc1)[N+](=O)[O-]	14.61255	1.03	1.0615	0.5205	Y
*100-02-7	O=[N+](O)c1ccc(O)cc1	15.86042	0.77	1.3736	0.5306	Y
*100-01-6	O=[N+](O)c1ccc(N)cc1	14.38971	0.95	1.0058	0.5235	Y
*95-57-8	Oc1ccccc1Cl	11.65710	0.08	0.3223	0.0641	Y
*106-48-9	Oc1ccc(Cl)cc1	12.16430	0.74	0.4492	0.1242	Y
*120-83-2	Clc1cc(Cl)c(O)cc1	14.47510	0.96	1.0271	0.2014	Y
*108-39-4	Cc1cc(O)ccc1	10.95830	0.08	0.1476	0.1108	Y
*100-41-4	CCc1ccccc1	12.50072	0.19	0.5333	0.0406	Y
*106-43-4	Cc1ccc(Cl)cc1	14.21392	0.82	0.9618	0.1140	Y
*371-41-5	Fc1ccc(O)cc1	10.36070	-0.32	-0.0019	0.1070	Y
*98-86-2	CC(=O)c1ccccc1	12.46862	0.26	0.5253	0.1800	Y
*93-58-3	COC(=O)c1ccccc1	14.31410	0.70	0.9868	0.1939	Y
*60-12-8	OCCc1ccccc1	11.04870	-0.46	0.1702	0.0546	Y
*99-91-2	O=C(C)c1ccc(Cl)cc1	14.77943	1.28	1.1032	0.2572	Y
*90-12-0	Cc2ccccc1ccccc12	19.34809	1.89	2.2458	0.0559	Y
*95-50-1	Clc1ccccc1Cl	14.91272	0.56	1.1366	0.0673	Y
*541-73-1	Clc1ccccc(Cl)c1	15.41992	0.65	1.2634	0.1274	Y

*) DA is domain of applicability according to inequality 6.

Table 4

Correlation weights for SA_k which were obtained in three runs of the Monte Carlo optimization

Lists	SA_k	$CW(SA_k)$	$CW(SA_k)$	$CW(SA_k)$	$N_{TRN}(SA_k)$	$N_{CLB}(SA_k)$	$N_{TST}(SA_k)$	SA_k -Defect
		Run 1	Run 2	Run 3				
	Promoters of $\log K_\infty$ increase							
1	c	1.10968	1.10473	1.26748	14	7	7	0.0032
2	BOND0000	0.70282	0.40330	0.69813	11	4	4	0.0108
3	O	1.83735	1.97617	1.86091	8	6	5	0.0139
4	(0.33750	0.44211	0.43895	7	7	6	0.0300
5	C	0.40855	0.38316	0.36132	7	2	3	0.0038
6	N	0.55203	0.80431	0.55981	5	3	2	0.0068
7	NOSP0000	3.99571	4.00215	4.00053	4	0	2	0.0032
8	=	0.89881	0.27293	1.32202	3	3	3	0.0381
9	BOND1000	1.25041	1.80481	0.97254	3	3	3	0.0381
10	Cl	1.71623	1.66733	1.62615	3	1	2	0.0171
11	2	1.05462	0.79527	0.80297	2	1	1	0.0032
12	Br	2.10086	1.90150	1.90447	2	0	0	1.0000
	Promoters of $\log K_\infty$ decrease							
1	1	-0.49548	-0.50230	-0.49734	15	7	7	0.0000
2	NOSP0100	-0.17308	-0.24565	-0.36530	6	4	3	0.0032
3	+	-0.49659	-0.35427	-0.44697	2	2	2	0.0381
4	-	-0.28549	-0.44694	-0.30472	2	2	2	0.0381
5	NOSP1100	-0.20356	-0.42131	-0.32212	2	2	2	0.0381
6	[-0.07625	-0.27823	-0.12118	2	2	2	0.0381
	Undefined							
1	NOSP1000	0.10002	-0.20099	0.00304	3	1	0	1.0000
	Blocked							
1	#	0.0	0.0	0.0	1	0	0	0.0000
2	BOND0100	0.0	0.0	0.0	1	0	0	0.0000
3	I	0.0	0.0	0.0	1	0	0	0.0000
4	/	0.0	0.0	0.0	0	1	0	0.0000
5	3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0	0	1	0.0000
6	\	0.0	0.0	0.0	0	1	0	0.0000

The $N_{TRN}(SA_k)$, $N_{CLB}(SA_k)$, and $N_{TST}(SA_k)$ are the frequencies of a SA_k in the sub-training set, calibration set, and test set, respectively.

Table 5

The compliance to the OECD principles [32] <http://www.oecd.org/env/ehs/risk-assessment/37849783.pdf>

	QSAR model (for regulatory purposes) should obeys the following five OECD principles:	How a principle is taken into account in this work?
1	a defined endpoint	The numerical data on the adsorption ($\log K_{\infty}$, mg/g) of organic contaminants (n=59) by MWCNTs taken in the literature [7].
2	an unambiguous algorithm	The Monte Carlo optimization which is represented by the CORAL software available on the Internet (http://www.insilico.eu/coral)
3	a defined domain of applicability	A substance falls in the domain of applicability if its SMILES obey the inequality 6: DefectSMILES < 2 * $\overline{\text{DefectSMILES}}$
4	appropriate measures of goodness-of-fit, robustness and predictivity	Large values of correlation coefficient and small root-mean-squared error for all sub-sets (i.e. the sub-training, calibration, test, and validation sets). The specific metrics $\overline{r_m^2}$ and Δr_m^2 for the test set [33]. The checking up a model for a group of different splits.
5	a mechanistic interpretation, if possible	Lists of stable promoters of $\log K_{\infty}$ increase and stable promoters of $\log K_{\infty}$ decrease (Table 5).

Table 6

Collection of links related to databases and software on nanomaterials

Link	Comments
http://www.insilicotox.com/index.php/blog/	QNAR Iron Oxides Toxicity. Software for models related to nanomaterials
http://teqip.jdvu.ac.in/QSAR_Tools/	Nano Profiler 1.2. Software for models related to nanomaterials
http://cordis.europa.eu/result/rcn/86196_en.html	Results of work of EU consortium aimed to build up database on nanomaterials endpoints.
https://ochem.eu/home/show.do?render-mode=popup	Multi-targets system of databases and software including data on nanomaterials
http://modern-fp7.biocenit.cat/	A system related to collect and predict toxicity of nanomaterials
http://nanograde.com/request-nanoparticle-formulations/	Commercial web site suggested synthesis of various nanoparticles
http://www2.mst.dk/Udgiv/publications/2013/09/978-87-93026-50-6.pdf	A series of projects regarding nanomaterials in Denmark (“Better control of nano”). Research of Dermal Penetration and Absorption of Nanomaterials
http://www.iom-world.org/news-events/news/2013/dermal-absorption-of-nanomaterials/	The Institute of Occupational Medicine (IOM) is a UK based leading provider of health and safety solutions to industry, commerce, public sector and professional bodies.
http://www.nanowerk.com/products/product.php?id=110	Nanowerk is system of databases on Nanomaterials
https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/research-topic/nanotechnology	The Joint Research Centre (JRC) is the European Commission's in-house science service. One of the targets of JRC is the systematization of data related to nanotechnology.

Figure 1. The definition of the $T^{\#}$ and $N^{\#}$ for the CORAL model. The r_{test}^2 is correlation coefficient between the experimental and calculated values of the $\log K_{\infty}$ for the test set.

Sub-training set (●), Calibration set (○), Test set (△), Validation set (▲)

Figure 2. The graphical representation for the CORAL models calculated with Eq. 7 (split 0) and with Eq. 8 (split 4)